

Table of Contents 1 Files of the holo and apo systems of HydroDock protocol as found in Dry_docking.tgz

Folder description	Input files	Output files	HydroDock Step
Dry_docking > holo or apo > PDB code of system	*.pdbqt files, containing the atomic coordinates of the ligand and the target with partial charges, grid.gpf and docking.dpf, files containing parameters for AutoGrid4 and AutoDock4 calculations	*.sta file containing the scoring values, O_rank_*.pdb files that are the output ranks of the docking, grid.glg and docking.dlg, output files of AutoGrid4 and AutoDock4 calculations	Step 1

Table of Contents 2 Files of the holo and apo systems of HydroDock protocol as found in MD.tgz

Folder description	Input files	Output files	HydroDock Step
MobyWat_result > holo or apo > PDB code of system	*_target_EM.pdb, energy minimized target protein PDB file, st.mdp, cg.mdp and md10ns.mdp, parameter files for steepest descent, conjugated gradient energy minimizations and MD simulation, system.xtc, trajectory file	O_system.log, log file, O_system.pli, pool information file, O_system.plw, pool waters file, O_system_prIDA.pdb, O_system_prIDA_top.pdb, short (top-cut) prediction list, O_system_tpy.pdb, topology file, complex_hyd.pdb, hydrated complex structure	Step 2
Refinement > holo or apo > PDB code of system	cg1.mdp, cg2.mdp, st1.mdp, st2.mdp and md.mdp, parameter files necessary to run five-step refinement		Step 3
MD_result > holo or apo > PDB code of system	after_cg2.gro, energy minimized structure resulted from Step 3, kdn.tpr, a portable binary run input file containing the simulation topology, coordinates, and parameters, md1.mdp, parameter file for MD simulation, posres.itp, topology include file with position restraints information, topol.top, topology file		Step 4